

Rights and Responsibilities of PRI Members in a Scheduled District of Odisha

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ABSTRACT

The role of Panchayati Raj Members in nation building is immiscible. They are the representative of the people to form the local self government and run the administration. If these representatives would properly aware about their rights and responsibilities, no executive members will lack in delivering public services. In this article a humble effort has made by the researchers to know the status of the awareness of the PRI members in a scheduled district of Odisha i.e. Nabarangpur. Interview schedules, formal and informal interviews, focus group discussions were conducted in order to find the status. Both Primary and secondary data were used for the study.

KEYWORDS: PRI, Roles, Responsibilities, Scheduled Areas, Challenges, Suggestions

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INTRODUCTION

In India, the concept of local self-government is not new. Throughout the ages until the British rule, the village communities have kept this system alive. In our villages, different sections of the community helped and depended on each other. Age-old customs and traditions helped to maintain the community spirit. Kingdoms were built and destroyed but these village communities maintained their shape and spirit. These very village bodies were the lines of contact with higher authorities on matters affecting the villages. Each village had a Sabha consisting of the adult residents of the village. Each Sabha had a sort of executive body of around five people known as panchayat. The panchayat was collectively responsible for looking after the needs of village people. Thus each village was a compact administrative unit served by public functionaries who were a part of the village community. These panchayats managed the affairs of the village community. No village affair was considered beyond

its control. Despite many of the political changes in cities and towns during the medieval period, the system of the local government or the panchayats in villages continued undisturbed. We have just outlined the ancient system of local government in our country. We have also told you that it has lived through the centuries in spite of several political changes. We will now discuss the history of the Panchayati Raj in India from the British period onwards. When the British came to India, we had our own village government system. Some among them (Charles Metcalf, for example) admired it and called panchayats "Little Republics". But, of course, the British used it to extend their own rule and power. Do you know how? The British had their own representatives in every region. As a result of the British interference, the attitude of the people towards panchayats changed. Progressively, the people began losing faith in the institution of panchayat. Other conditions too had changed. For example, direct

taxation gave way to indirect taxation. In many regions of the country, for example, in the North Western provinces, a leading or prominent person was put in charge of various jobs like construction, development work, etc. This system took the place of the local institutions like panchayats. In 1882, the Government of India Resolution on local self-government was announced. Lord Ripon's Government had sent circulars to the governments in the provinces on the subject of local self-government, as they wanted to find out what the public opinion was. The issues in the circular became the basis for the Government of India Resolution (1882) and later the Local Bodies Act of 1885 came into being. This was the basis for setting up local self-governing institutions with a majority of nominated members down to the village level. It seems that Lord Ripon viewed the problem of local self-government liberally. He thought that the local self-governing institutions would act as instruments of political and popular education. Another major step in this direction was the Report of the Royal Commission on Decentralization. This commission was set up in 1907 and it submitted its report in 1909. It recommended that it would be desirable for effective decentralization to associate people with local tasks and village affairs through village panchayats. But like the Ripon Resolution, the recommendations made by the Royal Commission on Decentralization also remained on paper only. In the same year (i.e. 1909), the 24th Session of the Congress at Lahore adopted a resolution urging the Government to take early steps to have elected local bodies from village panchayat upwards with non-official chairmen for the local bodies and to provide them necessary financial support. The Montagu-Chelmsford Reforms of 1919, under the proposed scheme of diarchy, made local self-government a "transferred subject". This meant that local self-government was brought under the control of Indian ministers in the provinces. The idea was to make the local bodies truly representative bodies by bringing them under the popular control. This, however, did not make the panchayat institutions truly democratic, as there were various other constraints to overcome. Yet many acts were passed by various states for establishing panchayats. These included 'Bengal Village Self-Government Act of 1919', 'Madras, Bombay and United Provinces Village Panchayat Act of 1920', 'Bihar and Orissa Village Administration Act', 'Assam Rural Self-Government Act of 1926', 'Punjab Village Panchayat Act of 1935', etc. These acts aimed at looking after the development of villages and their affairs. The local self-government had powers even to try minor cases. But these bodies were not democratic in the

real sense, because most of their members were not elected but nominated by the government. They had few powers given to them and their financial resources were also limited. The situation remained more or less the same till 1947.

POST-INDEPENDENCE PERIOD

The Indian National Congress perceived panchayats as people's institutions. Local self-governance was seen as the true voice of democracy. Many of our leaders, mainly Mahatma Gandhi, had pointed out that independence must begin at the lowest level. Every village should be a republic (Gram Swaraj) with a panchayat having full powers. The idea was to have democratic processes operating at the grass roots level as much as at the national level.

Birth of the Panchayati Raj System in Independent India

It was the Study Team on Community Projects and National Extension Services headed by Balwantrai Mehta and set up in 1957, which expressed concern about the lack of popular participation in Community Development Programmes and made a strong plea for devolution of power to lower levels through Panchayati Raj. Thus the Panchayati Raj system came into existence in 1959 with two basic objectives. These were (1) democratic decentralization and (2) local participation in planned programmes. This was a big step forward in the process of development. It was mentioned in the preceding unit that the Balwantrai Mehta Committee recommended a three-tier system of Panchayati Raj. In other words, the system had to work at three levels. They were: the district level (Zilla Parishad), the intermediate level (Block Samiti) and the lower level (Village Panchayat). The Committee suggested the setting up of Block Level Committees comprising elected representatives with adequate powers and resources for development programmes. The team felt that in this way Panchayati Raj system would be able to establish a link between the people and the government. The states of Rajasthan and Andhra Pradesh were the first to adopt this system. By 1959, all the states had passed Panchayat Acts, and by the mid-1960s, panchayats had been set up in all parts of the country, as more than 217,300 village panchayats, covering over 96 per cent of the 579,000 inhabited villages and 92 per cent of the rural population, had come into being. On an average, a panchayat represented a population of about 2,400 covering two to three villages. There was a lot of enthusiasm generated in the rural India and the people started feeling that they could have a say in the affairs affecting their daily lives. Unfortunately this enthusiasm could not be sustained. One explanation given is that

“strengthening of local government institutions and devolution of powers did not go hand in hand with adequate delegation and devolution of powers, particularly in respect of planning and administration”. On the other hand, national development planners were busy experimenting with other development initiatives, like the ‘Green Revolution’ in the 1960s and the ‘Target Group’ approach in the 1970s, as they were anxious partly to show overnight results in the food situation and partly to reach target groups to contain poverty. As a result local self-government system nourished through history and promised by the Constitution of India started languishing. It was only when development planners realized that community participation in development planning was not forthcoming on the expected lines and that the poverty situation was showing little signs of recovery, that we started looking back at local self-government through Panchayati Raj during the late 1970s. Thus the appointment of Ashoka Mehta Committee in 1977 marked a “turning point in the concept and practice of Panchayati Raj”.

Asoka Mehta Committee

In 1977, a committee was appointed under the chairmanship of Asoka Mehta to review the working of the Panchayati Raj Institutions. The Committee listed several factors responsible for the decline of the Panchayati Raj. They included: i) Dissociation of the programmes of development from the Panchayati Raj; ii) Inability of the bureaucracy to involve panchayats in the implementation of development programmes; iii) Internal deficiencies within the panchayat institutions; and iv) A lack of clarity about the concept itself. The Asoka Mehta Committee provided a definite philosophical treatment to the system. It observed that rural India was the backbone of all developmental programmes. The future of India would depend on the welfare of the villages. Panchayati Raj as a system should contribute to the philosophy and the functions of rural life in India. The most significant recommendation of the committee was about the two-tier Panchayati Raj system. According to this recommendation, the Zilla Parishad at the district level had to be established as the first point of decentralization. It also recommended the formation of Mandal Panchayats. A Mandal was conceived as a group of villages, which would make the necessary links with the system in developing focal points. It would also develop links between rural and urban areas. One major weakness of the Ashoka Mehta Committee was that it ignored the importance of the Gram Sabha.

G.V.K. Rao Committee

This Committee was set up in 1985. It was asked to look into the administrative arrangements for rural development and the role of panchayat bodies and their relationships with the administrative setup. With reference to the Panchayati Raj, we may recall the major recommendations of this committee as follows:

- Zilla Parishads (at district level) should be strengthened,
- There should be sub-committees at the district level with proportional representation,
- Some planning functions may be transferred to the district level, and
- Elections of local bodies should be held regularly. The committee believed that development was possible, only if a large number of people participated in development activities. In order to achieve this, adequate powers and financial resources at the local level were considered essential.

L.M. Singhvi Committee

This was set up in 1986. It gave importance to the Gram Sabha. Once again, the Gram Sabha was viewed as the seedbed of democracy. Some of its major recommendations are:

- Local self-government should be constitutionally recognized.
- Elections at the panchayat level should be held regularly and without delay.
- Panchayati Raj judicial tribunal should be set up in every state to deal with matters related to the working of Panchayati Raj.
- There should be adequate financial resources to ensure effective functioning of panchayats.
- Participation of individuals attached to political parties should be discouraged.
- The Nyaya Panchayat should be given the functions of mediation and settling of issues.

Sarkaria Commission

The Sarkaria Commission (1988), which was primarily concerned with the centre-state relationship, also recommended the strengthening of local bodies financially and functionally. The commission also believed that elections for panchayats must be held regularly. By the end of 1988, a sub-committee of the Consultative Committee of Parliament Rural Credit and Banking under the chairmanship of P.K. Thungon made recommendations for strengthening the Panchayati Raj system once again. One of its important recommendations was that Panchayati Raj bodies should be constitutionally recognized. Similarly, the Congress Committee headed by V.N. Gadgil in 1989 recommended a three-tier system of Panchayati Raj with a fixed term of 5 years for the elected members and reservation for Scheduled Castes/Tribes and women. The recommendations of these various committees and commissions generated a strong realization that there was a need to create a strong third layer of governance, which would help the rural community to influence its own future. To

materialize this, it was considered necessary to give constitutional recognition to the third layer of governance. It was against the backdrop of these recommendations by various committees and commissions that the Constitution (64th Amendment) Bill was drafted.

THE CONSTITUTION (73RD AMENDMENT) ACT, 1992

The amendment phase began with the 64th Amendment Bill (1989), which was introduced in Parliament for constituting panchayats in every state at the village, the intermediate and the district levels. It proposed that the Legislature of a State could by law endow the panchayats with such powers and authority as may be necessary to enable them to function as institutions of self-government. This bill was the brainchild of Rajiv Gandhi, who strongly believed in strengthening panchayats by giving them constitutional status. Unfortunately, though the Bill got two-thirds majority in the Lok Sabha, it was struck down in the Rajya Sabha on October 15, 1989 by just two votes. The next Government headed by V.P. Singh also made an abortive effort to provide constitutional status to panchayats through the introduction of the 74th Amendment Bill. Notwithstanding the above disappointments, the government declared its commitment to the philosophy of 'Power to the People', and so to providing the much needed constitutional status to panchayats. Accordingly, in September 1991, the 72nd Amendment of the Constitution was introduced. This was referred to a Joint Select Committee of the Parliament in December 1991 for detailed examination. Finally, after including necessary changes, the Amendment was passed with near unanimity in the Lok Sabha on December 22, 1992 and in the Rajya Sabha on December 23, 1992. Finally, on April 20, 1993 the President of India gave it his assent. This Amendment of the Constitution is known as the Constitution (Seventy-Third Amendment) Act, 1992. This Act was brought in to force by a notification with effect from April 24, 1993. This Act makes the details of the transfer of power to the Panchayat a part of the most basic document of this nation: the Constitution of India. By virtue of this Act, no one will be able to take away the powers, responsibilities and finances given to the Panchayats. They are expected to play a much bigger role in the development of their respective areas and people. It is also expected that everyone will be able to take part in this process including the poorest of the poor. All of us know that the objective of national development can be achieved only through the development of the vast rural areas. People who are poor and unemployed cannot have adequate buying

power. You must have seen that even nature does not favour us every time. From time to time, we have to face failures of the monsoon, droughts, floods, cyclones, etc. It is now hoped that through people's involvement, panchayats will be able to play a more responsible role in overcoming these difficulties.

Scheduled Areas:-

Article 244(1) denotes, the provision of the Fifth Schedule shall apply to the administration & control of scheduled areas & scheduled tribes in any state other than north eastern areas. The areas are (1) Andhra Pradesh (2) Bihar (3) Gujarat (4) Madhya Pradesh (5) Maharashtra (6) Odisha (7) Himachal Pradesh (8) Rajasthan. The scheme of administration of scheduled areas under the fifth schedule visualizes a division of responsibility between the state & union government. The state government has been given the responsibility of screening the legislation which is unsuitable for extension to the tribal areas. They are also responsible for framing regulation which is necessary for the protection of the tribals' land & for prevention of exploitation of the tribal by the money lenders. The Union Government provides guidelines & necessary funds that are required to raise the standard of administration & for the improvement in the quality of life of the tribal communities. The Governor of those states which have Scheduled Areas is empowered under the Fifth Schedule with the right to modify central & state laws so as to make them applicable to Tribal Areas. The said Governor is also required to submit an annual report to the President of India regarding administration of Scheduled Areas. In addition to this there is a provision of establishing tribal advisory councils.

Scheduled Areas of Odisha

In exercise of powers conferred by sub-paragraph 6 of the Fifth Schedule to the Constitution of India, the revised Presidential Order titled "The Scheduled Areas (states of Bihar, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh & Odisha) Order 1977" has declared the full districts viz. Mayurbhanj, Sundargarh, Koraput (which now includes the districts of Koraput, Malkangiri, Nabarangapur and Rayagada), Kuchinda tahasil of Sambalpur district, Keonjhar, Telkoi, Champua, Barbil tahasils of Keonjhar district, Khondamal, Balliguda and G.Udayagiri tahasil of Khondamal district, R.Udaygiri tahasil, Gumma and Rayagada block of Parlekhemundi tahasil in Parlakhemundi Sub-division and Suruda tahasil (excluding Gazalbadi and Gochha Gram Panchayats), of Ghumsur sub-division in Ganjam district, Thuamul Rampur and Lanjigarh blocks of Kalahandi district and Nilagiri block of Balasore district as Scheduled Areas of the state. After reorganisation of districts in the state, 7

districts fully and 6 districts partly are covered under the Scheduled Areas of the state.

The scheduled tribe population of Odisha is 81,45,081(2011 census), which constitute 22.84% of the total population of the state. The tribal population of Odisha is 9.7% of the total tribal population of India. Odisha has the unique distinction of being the homeland of the highest number of tribal communities (62) & the largest number of particularly vulnerable tribal Groups (Previously known as Primitive tribal Groups) which is (13) thirteen in numbers. Each tribal community is distinct in terms of their traditional cultural practices like dance, arts & crafts etc. They are in majority in 118 out of 314 Blocks. Table 1.10 gives us information about the population of scheduled tribes of Odisha state from the census of 1961 to 2011. Malkangiri district has the highest proportion of STs, (57.4%) & followed by Mayurbhanj (56.6%), Rayagada (55.8%) & Nabarangpur (55%), Puri district has the lowest proportion of STs (0.3%) Khond is the most populous tribe followed by Gond. The other major tribals living in Odisha are Santal, Kolha, Munda, Saora, Shabar, Bhattada, Bhumij, Bhuiya, Oraon, and Paroja & Kisan.

THE PROVISIONS OF THE PANCHAYATS (EXTENSION TO THE SCHEDULED AREAS) ACT, 1996

The Provisions of the Panchayats (Extension to the Scheduled Areas) Act, 1996 came into force on December 24, 1996. This Act extends panchayats to the tribal areas of the states such as Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Orissa and Rajasthan. It intends to enable tribal societies to assume control over their destiny and to preserve and conserve their traditional rights over natural resources. The State Governments were required to enact their legislations in accordance with the provisions of the Act within one year, i.e. by

December 23, 1997. Most of the states have enacted the required state legislation to give effect to the provisions contained in Act 14, 1996. The salient features of the Act are: 1) Every village shall have an elected Gram Sabha and it shall be competent to safeguard and preserve the traditions and customs of the people. 2) Gram Sabha shall approve the plans, programmes and projects for social and economic development before their implementation. 3) It would be responsible for the identification or selection of persons as beneficiaries under the poverty alleviation and other programmes. 4) Every Gram Panchayat shall obtain from the related Gram Sabha a certificate of utilization of funds for the plans, programmes and projects. 5) The reservation of seats in the Scheduled Areas in every panchayat shall be in the proportion of the populations of the communities in the panchayat. 6) Planning and management of minor water bodies in the Scheduled Areas shall be entrusted to panchayats at the appropriate level. 7) Recommendations of the Gram Sabha or the panchayats shall be mandatory for granting i) licenses for mining minerals, and ii) concessions for the exploitation of minor minerals by auction in the Scheduled Areas. 8) The state legislature shall endow panchayats and the Gram Sabha specifically with: i) the power to enforce prohibition or regulate or restrict the sale and consumption of any intoxicant; ii) the ownership of minor forest produce; iii) the power to prevent land alienation in the Scheduled Areas; iv) the power to manage village markets; v) the power to control money lending to Scheduled Tribes and social sectors; vi) the power to control local plans and resources for such plans, including tribal sub-plans; and vii) the state legislations that may endow panchayats with powers and authority, as may be necessary to enable them to function as institutions of selfgovernment, and contain safeguards to ensure that panchayats at the higher level do not assume the powers and authority of any panchayats at the lower level or of the Gram Sabha.

Diagrammatical Representation of the Local Self Government

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the role of PRI members in development of the Gram Panchayat as instructed by the provisions
2. To study the present scenario of developmental works in the study area
3. To enquire about the steps performed by the PRI members in the study area for development
4. To aware the PRI members about their rights and responsibilities
5. To suggest certain measures for successful functioning of the PRI members which would lead to further socio-economic empowerment of the stakeholders.

Hypotheses

1. PRI members are not properly trained about their rights and responsibilities
2. Though women representatives were there, but they are rubber stamp, real works are done by their spouse
3. Block administration were not conducting awareness programmes for PRI members properly, as a result they are not utilizing their duties optimally.

Methodology

Universe

The Nabarangpur district is the universe for the proposed study

Census

The Tentulikhunti block of Nabarangpur district is the census for the proposed study

Sample & Sampling ,Tools and Techniques

Out of 15 Gram Panchayats of Tentulikhunti block, 02 Panchayats namely Pujariguda

Tentulikhunti would selected on the basis of simple random sample method. There are 03 Revenue Villages were there in Pujariguda GP & 09 Revenue Villages were there in Tentulikhunti GP. All the word members, Samiti Members and Zilla Parishad Members associated with this area were interviewed with the Structured Interview Schedule, Focus Group Discussion. Simple statistical tools like average, percentage, etc will be used to analyse the data collected and diagrams like Pie-chart, Bar-Diagram will be used to present the analysis in graphical/ photo pictorial forms.

DISTRICT PROFILE: NABARANGPUR

1. Area and Location:

The district of Nabarangpur came into existence on 2nd October 1992 after being carved out of the erstwhile Koraput district. The district is located in south western corner of Odisha and bounded by Kalahandi and Koraput districts in east and south, and the Raipur and Bastar districts of Chattisgarh in the north and west respectively. Nabarangpur district is located at 81° 52' to 82° 53' E longitude and 19° 9' to 20° 5' N latitude and stretches over an area of approximately 5291 sq.km. It shares 3.40 % of landmark of the State and occupies 14th rank in term of area.

2. Population:

As per 2011 census, the total population of Nabarangpur district is 12,20,946 comprising of 11,33,321 rural and 87,625 urban population. The SC and ST population constituted 14.5 % and 55.8 % of the district population respectively. The district is predominantly inhabited by tribals like Kandha, Paraja, Soura etc. The density of population per sq.km is 231 with decadal growth rate of 19.0 for the district, as against population density of 270 person per sq.km and decadal growth rate of 14.0 for the state. It has 891 census villages (including 23 uninhabited villages) covering 10 Blocks and 10 Tahasils. The literacy percentage of the district is 46.4 against 72.9 of the state. The level of urbanization stands at 7.18% of the total district population as against the 0.21% of the State.

3. Climate:

Nabarangpur district falls under East Coast Plains and Hills as per the GOI's AgroClimatic Zonal Planning. Entire district except Dabugan block, falls under 'Eastern Ghat High lands'. Dabugan block falls under 'Western undulating lands'. The climate is subtropical to temperate. It is characterized by hot and dry summer, cool and humid monsoon and cold and dry winter. The district has different types of soils like red and laterite. The soil PH is neutral to alkaline and its salinity is normal. In 2018 Normal rainfall of the district was 1569.5 mm and the actual rainfall was 1382.7 mm.

4. Agriculture:

Agriculture is the prime occupation/activity in the district. During the year 2017- 18, the net area sown was 152 thousand hectares against 3863 thousand hectares of the state. The major crops grown are paddy, ragi, maize,

niger, pulses and wheat. Maize is being grown extensively in Umerkote, Raighar and Jharigan Blocks. The production of paddy was 4661515 quintals, Maize 644811 quintals, Ragi 4 quintals, Mung 6251 quintals, Biri 22872 quintals, Kulthi 15308 quintals, Groundnuts 233 quintals, Potatoes 21385 quintals and Sugarcane 93715 quintals. The yield rate of paddy was 37.33 Qtl/ha, Ragi 0.62 Qtl/ha, Maize 31.47 Qtl/ha. During 2017-18, the total fertilizer used in this district was about 38498 MT out of which Nitrogenous fertilizer has a share of 26515 MT, Phosphatic 7369 MT and Pottasic 4614 MT. The consumption of fertilizer per hectare stood at 151.03 Kg.

5. Irrigation:

It is reported by the D.A.O, Nabarangapur during 2017-18. The irrigation potential created during Kharif and Rabi are 54409 and 34181 hectares respectively from different sources. This is 16.74% of net area sown during Kharif & Rabi season respectively.

6. Co-operation:

The district has 13 agricultural Co-operative societies with a membership of 165100. The loan advances is to the tune of Rs. 17229.65 lakh and loan outstanding stood at Rs. 12365.68 lakhs as of 2017-18. The agricultural credit Co-operative societies as more or less evenly distributed across the 10 Blocks of the district. Besides that are 4 non-agricultural credit Co-operative Societies in the district of which 3 are in Nabarangpur Municipalities and 1 in Jharigaon Block. These are 2 marketing Co-operative Societies one each in Nabarangpur (M) & Umerkote (M).

7. Forest:

District of Nabarangpur has abundant of Forest area that contributed 46.55% of the total geographical area of the district.

8. Animal Husbandry:

Animal Husbandry offers a good potential for rural employment in Nabarangpur District, owing to the longer tradition of homestead animal husbandry practiced by the tribal population and abundance of ingredients of feed i.e. maize, horse gram and oil cakes. During 2017-18, Milk production is 28.86 thousand MT, production of eggs is 155.21 lakhs nos. and production of meat is 3.12 thousand MT in this district. During 2017-18, 16 nos. of Hospitals and Dispensaries, 87 nos. of Livestock Aid centers and 71 Artificial Insemination Centers were functioning in the district.

9. Industry and Mining:

The only medium scale industry in the district is Mangalam Timber Products Ltd. In addition to this there are few rice mills, an oil mills, a cotton spinning unit and a pharmaceutical units. There is huge potential for Maize processing industries. During the year 2017-18, 1024 nos. of Micro small and Medium Enterprise have established with total capital investment of about Rs.4782.58 lakhs with 3096 nos. of employment generated in this district. Artisan clusters are there in the field of tribal jewellery, terracotta, wood/ bamboo craft, lacquer work, weaving, dhokra casting, paddy craft, etc. No mines are there in this district.

10. Power:

There are 820 revenue villages electrified as on 31.03.2018 which constitutes 94.5 % to the total villages of the district.

11. Transport & Communication:

The district is not connected with railway routes. The district has 42 km. of National Highways, 123 kms of State Highways, 64 kms of Major District Road, 421 kms of other district roads, 1905 kms of Rural Roads, 136 kms of Forest Roads, 3822 kms of Inter-village Roads and 2352 kms of Intra-village Roads. All the Block Headquarters 3 are connected with the State Capital by road only. Inter-State buses are plying to Andhra Pradesh (Vizianagram, Visakhapatnam, etc.) and Chattisgarh (Raipur, Jagdalpur, etc.).

12. Education:

During 2017-18, there were 1217 nos. of primary schools, 625 nos. of upper primary, 210 nos. of secondary schools and 19 nos. of general colleges in the district. The teacher pupil ratio in the primary, upper primary, Secondary School stood at 34, 26 and 37 respectively.

13. Health:

The medical facilities are provided by different agencies like Govt., Private medicals and voluntary organizations in the district. During 2017-18, there were 2 nos. Allopathic medical Institutions/Hospital, 10 nos. of CHCs, 40 nos. of PHCs, 289 nos. of Sub-centers and one no of private Hospital functioning in the district. Only 16 nos. of Homoeopathic dispensaries and 22 nos. of Ayurvedic dispensaries are in the district.

14. Banking:

As on March' 2018, there were 63 nos. of All Banks having 3245.76 crore rupees deposit and 1744.37 crore rupees credit in the district. The district has banking branches network of 63 out of which 0 (0%) were in the urban area, 25 (39.68%) in semi-urban area and 38 (60.32%) in rural areas. The total number of ATMs in the district stood at 56.

15. Collection of Land Revenue:

The total collection of land revenue in the district for 2017-18 was Rs. 1569.16 lakh. The total collection of Tax in the district during 2017-18 was Rs. 2368.56 Lakh.

16. Poverty Alleviation Programme:

In the district total no. of Job card issued was 2.38 Lakh and total no. of person days generated was 35.51 lakh during the year 2017-18. 17. Disaster Scenario: In terms of Disaster activity the district is graded as slight zone for wind & cyclone, high risk zone for flood, very high risk zone for drought, moderate risk zone for earthquake & high risk zone for accident.

Result of Interaction with Interview Schedule, Focus Group Discussion**Table No. -1.01-Details of Elected Representative of Pujari Guda GP**

Name of the GP, Sarpanch & Naib Sarpanch	SI No.	Name of the RV	Name of the PRI Member	Position/ Gender(M/F)
Pujariguda	1.	Khunti Padar	Sukadev Santa	Ward Member(M)
	2.	Bageipadar	Purna Bhatra	Ward Member(F)
	3.	Sira Guda	Balram Majhi	Ward Member(M)
	4.	Dani Guda	Nira Harijan	Ward Member(M)
	5.	Kuja Daniguda	Hema Jani	Ward Member(F)
Sarpanch- Kumar Pujari(M)	6.	Bisaguda	Annakranti Harijan	Ward Member(F) Cum Naib Sarpanch
	7.	Nuaguda	Chandal Jani	Ward Member(M)
	8.	Kurmakote-01	Arjun Karkara	Ward Member(M)
Naib Sarpanch- Annakranti Harijan(F)	9.	Kurmakote-02	Adae Jani	Ward Member(F)
	10.	Pujariguda-01	Narsingh Gouda	Ward Member(M)
	11.	Pujariguda-02	Aswasini Bhatra	Ward Member(F)
	12.	Pujariguda-03	Minakshi Bisoi	Ward Member(F)
	13.	Pujariguda-04	Lachhadei Majhi	Ward Member(F)

Table No. -1.02-Details of Elected Representative of Tentuli Khunti GP

Name of the GP, Sarpanch & Naib Sarpanch	SI No.	Name of the RV	Name of the PRI Member	Position/ Gender(M/F)
Tentuli Khunti,	1.	Tentulikhunti	Ichhabati Jani	Ward Member(F)
			Rukuni Suna	Ward Member(F)
			Rukuni Jani	Ward Member(F)
			Lingaraj Bhanja	Ward Member(M)
Sarpanch- Mrutyunjay Nayak(M)	2.	Udaypur	Santi Devi Singh	Ward Member(F)
			Kumari Jani	Ward Member(F)
			Damburu Muduli	Ward Member(M)
			Baidanath Majhi	Ward Member(M)
Naib Sarpanch- Santidevi Singh(F)	3.	Dangasil	Trinath Naik	Ward Member(M)
	4.	Khandiaguda	Samati Muduli	Ward Member(F)
			Nilan Bhatra	Ward Member(M)
	5.	Tabhapadar	Dasa Harijan	Ward Member(M)
	6.	Merakani	Merged with Tabhapadar	
	7.	Madagulumi	Leli Lohra	Ward Member(M)
8.	Panganmara	Sumitra Bagh	Ward Member(F)	
9.	Mangardara	Sunamajhi Jani	Ward Member(M)	
10.	Mundaguda	Merged with Mangardara		

Sl. No	Name of the Elected Representative	Position
1.	Geetanjali Bhatra	Samiti Sabhya
2.	Devaki Nayak	Panchayat Samiti Chairman
3.	Champabati Muduli	Zilla Parishad Sabhya

The following observation and analysis were made after interviewing the respondents

- Health:** There are sub centre (health) in each of the GP, where ANM (Auxiliary Nurse Midwife) were employed, who is associated with ASHA worker (Associated Social Health Activist), also Anganwadi workers were also looks after health issues of the inhabitants. Veterinary Office is also there at the GP headquarter, in which a VAS (Veterinary assistant surgeon) is employed who is dealing with cattle.
- Development of the weaker section:** As the study area is an scheduled areas, all the facilities provided by the government is enjoyed by them. For the purpose of Divyangs, after the certificate given by the doctor, appropriate steps were taken by the representatives. For the purpose of 60% disability a monthly pension of ₹ 700/- and ₹ 500/- is provided to the Divyangs with less than 60%.
- Maintenance of Infrastructure:** Regarding construction and maintenance of Roads, bridges, tanks, drain and wells, the PRI members sits at least once at the last of the month, where these kind of issues were represented and from which account the funds will be raised has analyzed at that meeting. The heads like, SFC (State Finance Commission), CFC (Central Finance Commission) were there, further there is provision in MGNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Assurance) in which works were undertaken.
- Drinking Water:** For the purpose of supplying clean drinking water, two over head tanks with the capacity of 10,000/- liters were constructed in each of the GP. For new connection ₹ 1000/- is charged by the beneficiary and a monthly rent of ₹ 100/- is paid by them in order to ensure drinking water supply.
- Roads & Drains:** As it is a rural area, regular cleaning of drain is not required as the establishment were not a planned one. Once in a year before Rainy season the drains were cleaned by the GP. Further there is Dustbins were set by the GP in the areas where large chunk of dirty materials were deposited by the inhabitants.
- Education:** There are 09 primary schools and 04 High School were in Pujari Guda GP and only 10 primary schools were there in Tentulikhunti GP. A School Management Committee was there where these representatives were having a voice. Further they are looking after toilet and water connection issues, making ramps for the Divyangs, maintenance of the flooring of the schools, construction of school boundary etc. These proposals were given to the block level officials through the Panchayat Executive Officer.
- Development of Cremation Ground:** There are two communities of people were there in the GPs, i.e., Hindu and Christian. In each of the Cremation Ground and Rest Shed has been developed in each of the GP.
- For Cattle:** In the House hold where Cattle rearing is practiced, a provision of construction of Cow-Shed is there. Earlier the fund of ₹ 48000/- was there but now it has hiked into ₹ 113000/- ; irrespective of the caste and community, every stake holder can avail this facility.
- Checking of Communicable Diseases:** All the PRI members were aware about the communicable diseases. Block administration were also organizing awareness campaign regarding the same. In the time of CORONA, it is ensured by the PRI members through the ASHA, Anganwadi workers and ANMs, whether the stakeholders were getting vaccinated or not, whether taken 2nd dose or not. Medicines were also distributed by these health workers for other diseases including COVID-19.
- Regarding Birth and Death Registration:** Though there is provision of registering birth and death, but they were not aware about the same. The researchers were guided them to ensure it at their respective GPs by consulting with the Block Administration.
- Regarding Fairs and Festivals:** As it is a scheduled area, inhabited by the tribal people, they are very cultural. In all most all of the months they are having festivals. Its ensured by the PRI members how to maintain discipline in those events and how the peoples will get maximum satisfaction by enjoying night shows which are organized at community level under the supervision of the PRIs. Weekly market is also

there in both of the GPs, for whom Verandah (Open Complex) has constructed by the GP and has been maintained.

12. Play Ground: There are two play ground in Pujariguda GP where as 01 play ground is there in Tentulikhunti GP. A gallery for sitting of the viewers is also attached to one of the play ground where main tournaments have been organized. They were in the process of constructing another mini stadium.

13. Education & Literacy: Literacy mission was organized by the government of Odisha during 1990s, but after that no steps were taken by the Odisha govt. The literacy of the Pujariguda GP is 58.54% whereas the literacy of Tentulikhunti GP is 61.32%. It is inspired by the researcher to the PRI members to provide written name of the illiterate person to the concerned persons as a result, they may practice their name and may became literate in due course of time.

Conclusion

It seems that the PRI members were average aware about their right and duties. More and more awareness programmes should be conducted by the block administration; as they have said that only three

days awareness programmes has been conducted by the block administration, when they were elected. They are also demanding for pensions and insurance, which may inspire them to do the works properly. They may be given the facility of exposure visit by which their outer knowledge may develop. If with courage and wisdom her leader have the sagacity to work with aid of science there is no reason that why India should remain forever poor.

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